

FACTORS AFFECTING IMPULSIVE PURCHASING BEHAVIOR OF EMPLOYEES IN DAPITAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

Impulsive purchasing behavior significantly influences consumer spending and retail sales in today's competitive business environment. This study completed on December 2024 examined the factors affecting impulsive purchasing behavior among employees in Dapitan City, particularly in terms of store ambiance, store layout, product price, and personality and self-concept. The study employed a quantitative descriptive research design using a survey questionnaire adapted from related studies. A total of 300 employees from government and private sectors were selected on through proportional random sampling. Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and Somer's D Test. Findings revealed that respondents strongly agreed that store ambiance, store layout, product price, and personality and self-concept influenced their impulsive purchasing behavior, with product price identified as the most influential factor. Employees also exhibited impulsive purchasing behaviors characterized by spontaneous buying, emotional attraction to products, shopping satisfaction, and unplanned decision-making. Furthermore, store layout, product price, and personality and self-concept showed significant relationships with impulsive purchasing behavior, while store ambiance showed no significant relationship. The study concluded that both internal and external factors significantly influence impulsive purchasing behavior among employees. The findings may provide valuable insights for retailers, marketers, consumers, and future researchers in understanding consumer purchasing behavior and improving marketing strategies.

Keywords: *impulsive purchasing behavior, consumer behavior, product price, store layout, employees, Dapitan City*

INTRODUCTION

Impulsive purchasing behavior has become an important aspect of consumer behavior because it significantly contributes to business sales and profitability. In today's competitive business environment, understanding consumer purchasing behavior is essential for developing effective marketing strategies. External factors such as store ambiance, store layout, product displays, and pricing greatly influence consumers' impulsive buying decisions. Likewise, marketing strategies such as product sampling and promotional activities encourage consumers to try new products and increase the likelihood of unplanned purchases. Impulsive buying is often driven by excitement, pleasure, and spontaneous decision-making, making it an important factor that affects overall consumer spending. It also emphasizes the importance of effective marketing practices in influencing consumer purchasing behavior and improving business performance (Huo et al., 2023). Further, Sohn and Ko (2021) emphasized that although all impulsive purchases are considered unplanned, not all unplanned purchases can be classified as impulsive. Unplanned purchases may occur because consumers need certain products that were not initially included on their shopping lists. In contrast, impulsive purchases are largely triggered by sensory experiences and external stimuli such as store ambiance, layout, and product pricing. Aside from these external influences, internal factors such as personality and self-concept also contribute to impulsive purchasing behavior.

Furthermore, physical stores are more likely to encourage impulsive purchasing behavior than online shopping platforms because they provide stronger sensory and emotional stimulation. Factors such as store ambiance, lighting, music, product displays, and direct product interaction increase consumers' excitement and spontaneous buying decisions. Although online shopping platforms use digital marketing strategies to encourage purchases, they cannot fully provide the sensory experience and immediate gratification available in physical stores. In the Philippine context, consumers still prefer physical stores because they allow direct product interaction and immediate product availability, which further influence impulsive buying behavior (Bhathena, 2025; Chandrasekhar et al., 2024).

Physical shopping environments continue to have a stronger influence on impulsive purchasing behavior compared to online shopping platforms. Recent studies revealed that sensory elements such as lighting, music, store layout, product displays, and direct product interaction stimulate consumers' emotions and encourage spontaneous purchasing decisions. Researchers also explained that physical stores provide immediate gratification and emotional excitement, which increase the likelihood of impulse buying. In contrast, online shopping platforms are less capable of stimulating consumers' five senses, making them comparatively less effective in encouraging impulsive purchases (Bhathena, 2025; Parsad et al., 2023).

Moreover, recent studies described impulsive purchasing behavior as spontaneous, unplanned, and emotionally driven. Consumers often make impulsive purchases because of excitement, pleasure, curiosity, and sudden emotional attraction

toward products. Studies further revealed that impulse buying significantly contributes to retail sales and consumer spending worldwide, demonstrating its economic importance in the business sector. Researchers also noted that impulsive purchasing behavior remains one of the most widely studied areas in consumer behavior because a large percentage of consumer purchases are made impulsively, greatly influencing marketing strategies, retail performance, and business profitability (Bhathena, 2025; Chandrasekhar et al., 2024; Parsad et al., 2023).

Despite the growing body of literature on impulsive purchasing behavior, most existing studies focused on general consumers, online shoppers, and retail customers in foreign settings. Limited studies have specifically examined the impulsive purchasing behavior of employees within the local context of Dapitan City. Furthermore, there is still insufficient information regarding how internal and external factors influence employees' impulsive purchasing decisions in physical shopping environments. This gap in the literature highlights the need for further investigation to better understand the factors affecting impulsive purchasing behavior among employees in Dapitan City.

Hence, this study aimed to determine the factors affecting impulsive purchasing behavior among employees in Dapitan City in 2024. The findings of this study may provide valuable information to business establishments, consumers, and future researchers in understanding and addressing impulsive purchasing behavior.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the factors affecting impulsive purchasing behavior among employees in Dapitan City during the year 2024.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the employees in Dapitan City in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. marital status;
 - 1.4. educational attainment;
 - 1.5. monthly income; and
 - 1.6. nature of employment?
2. How do the employees in Dapitan City perceive the factors affecting impulsive purchasing behavior in terms of:
 - 2.1. store ambiance;
 - 2.2. store layout;
 - 2.3. product price; and
 - 2.4. personality and self-concept?
3. What is the level of impulsive purchasing behavior among employees in Dapitan City?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the factors affecting impulsive purchasing behavior and the impulsive purchasing behavior of employees in Dapitan City?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a quantitative descriptive research design to systematically gather and analyze data regarding the impulsive purchasing behavior of employees from both government and private sectors. A survey questionnaire served as the primary instrument in collecting the necessary data from 300 respondents selected through proportional random sampling from various offices and establishments within Dapitan City.

The research instrument was adapted and slightly modified from existing studies related to impulsive purchasing behavior, specifically focusing on store ambiance, store layout, product price, personality, and self-concept. The questionnaire was composed of three sections: respondents' demographic profile, factors affecting impulsive purchasing behavior, and impulsive purchasing behavior. To ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument, pilot testing and reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha were conducted, confirming the consistency and suitability of the questionnaire for the study.

A five-point Likert scale was utilized to measure the respondents' perceptions and level of agreement with each statement in the questionnaire. Data gathering involved the personal distribution of questionnaires by the researchers after securing respondents' consent and ensuring confidentiality of responses. The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools such as frequency counting, frequency distribution, percentage computation, weighted mean, and Somer's D Test to determine the relationship between the identified factors and impulsive purchasing behavior. Ethical considerations were likewise observed to protect the rights, privacy, and welfare of the respondents throughout the conduct of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section analyzed the responses of the three hundred (300) employees from Dapitan City. The responses were treated statistically in order to answer the research questions of the present investigation.

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the 300 respondents included in the study. In terms of age, the majority of the respondents were aged 26–35 years old, with 106 respondents or 35.3%, followed by those aged 18–25 years old with 73 respondents or 24.3%. Respondents aged 36–45 years old comprised 61 or 20.3%, while 60 respondents or 20.0% were aged 46–55 years old and above. These findings indicate that most of the respondents were young to middle-aged adults who are actively engaged in employment and purchasing activities. In support, Urošević et al. (2023) pointed out that young and middle-aged adults are more actively engaged in purchasing activities and are more exposed to impulsive buying tendencies due to greater purchasing power and lifestyle demands. Recent studies revealed that age significantly influences impulsive

purchasing behavior because younger consumers are more likely to respond emotionally to promotional and environmental stimuli while shopping.

In terms of sex, female respondents dominated the study with 175 or 58.3%, while male respondents accounted for 125 or 41.7%. This implies that female employees were more represented in the study population. In support, Basalma (2024) pointed out that women are generally more engaged in shopping activities and are more emotionally responsive to marketing stimuli, making them more prone to impulsive purchases. Research on impulsive consumer behavior found that gender differences influence purchasing decisions, particularly in retail and shopping environments.

Regarding marital status, the majority of the respondents were married, with 199 respondents or 66.3%. Single respondents comprised 82 or 27.3%, while widowed respondents accounted for 19 or 6.3%. This indicates that most respondents had family responsibilities, which may influence their purchasing behavior. In support, Urošević et al. (2023) explaining that marital status may influence spending priorities and purchasing behavior due to family responsibilities and household needs. Married individuals often participate more frequently in shopping activities for family consumption, which may increase exposure to impulsive buying situations.

As to educational attainment, most respondents were college graduates, with 173 or 57.7%, followed by college-level respondents with 92 or 30.7%. Meanwhile, 18 respondents or 6.0% were high school graduates, 12 or 4.0% were high school level, 4 or 1.3% were elementary graduates, and only 1 respondent or 0.3% was elementary level. The findings suggest that the majority of respondents had attained higher levels of education. In support, Basalma (2024) revealed that individuals with higher educational attainment are more exposed to modern marketing platforms, digital promotions, and consumer trends, which may influence impulsive purchasing tendencies.

In terms of monthly income, the largest group of respondents earned PHP 10,000–20,000 monthly, with 128 or 42.7%, followed by those earning PHP 21,000–30,000 with 103 or 34.3%. Respondents earning PHP 31,000–40,000 accounted for 44 or 14.7%, while 23 respondents or 8.3% earned PHP 41,000–50,000. This indicates that most respondents belonged to the low- to middle-income bracket. In support, Chaudhuri et al. (2021) revealed that income significantly affects impulsive buying behavior. Consumers with stable income levels are more likely to engage in impulsive purchases because they possess greater financial capability and purchasing freedom. Research further emphasized that income level influences consumer confidence and willingness to spend on unplanned purchases.

Lastly, in terms of nature of employment, government employees comprised the majority with 160 respondents or 53.3%, while private employees accounted for 140 or 46.7%. This implies that both government and private sector employees were adequately

represented in the study. In support, Azul et al. (2023) revealed that employment status and occupational stability influence consumer spending behavior. Employees with stable sources of income tend to participate more actively in purchasing activities and are more exposed to retail environments that may trigger impulsive buying behavior.

Table 1.
Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age	18–25 years old	73	24.3
	26–35 years old	106	35.3
	36–45 years old	61	20.3
	46–55 and above	60	20.0
Sex	Male	125	41.7
	Female	175	58.3
Marital Status	Single	82	27.3
	Married	199	66.3
	Widow	19	6.3
Educational Attainment	College Graduate	173	57.7
	College Level	92	30.7
	High School Graduate	18	6.0
	High School Level	12	4.0
	Elementary Graduate	4	1.3
Monthly Income	Elementary Level	1	0.3
	PHP 10,000–20,000	128	42.7
	PHP 21,000–30,000	103	34.3
	PHP 31,000–40,000	44	14.7
Nature of Employment	PHP 41,000–50,000	23	8.3
	Government	160	53.3
	Private	140	46.7

Table 2
Factors Affecting Impulsive Purchasing Behavior of Employees

Factors	Statements	Mean	Description
Store Ambiance	The cleanliness and hygiene of the store make me feel comfortable and encourage me to shop.	4.57	Strongly Agree
	Well-organized and neatly displayed products improve my shopping experience.	4.44	Strongly Agree
	The lighting and decor of the store influence my perception of the products and make me more likely to purchase.	4.33	Strongly Agree
	A calm, air-conditioned shopping environment motivates me to stay longer and shop more.	4.38	Strongly Agree
	Attractive shelf designs and displays catch my attention and influence my buying decisions.	4.42	Strongly Agree
	Average Weighted Mean	4.43	Strongly Agree
Store Layout	The way products are arranged in the store often leads me to discover and buy items I didn't plan for.	4.18	Agree
	Substitutes placed together make it easier for me to compare and switch brands impulsively.	4.19	Agree
	Having enough space between aisles makes shopping enjoyable and less stressful.	4.13	Agree
	Clearly marked categories and special offer sections tempt me to buy unplanned items.	4.19	Agree
	Impulse purchases often happen when products are displayed near the checkout counter.	4.26	Strongly Agree
	Average Weighted Mean	4.19	Agree
Product Price	I am more likely to buy products on sale, even if I don't need them immediately.	4.65	Strongly Agree
	Discounts and promotions heavily influence my decision to purchase items.	4.62	Strongly Agree
	When shopping, I prioritize items that offer value for money over high-priced alternatives.	4.59	Strongly Agree
	I often choose cheaper options, even if it means compromising on quality.	4.58	Strongly Agree

Factors	Statements	Mean	Description
	My purchasing decisions are guided by price, especially when I am on a budget.	4.63	Strongly Agree
	Average Weighted Mean	4.61	Strongly Agree
Personality and Self-Concept	I tend to avoid unnecessary purchases when I feel tired or stressed.	4.27	Strongly Agree
	Shopping with friends often leads me to buy items I wouldn't normally consider.	3.78	Agree
	My emotional state influences my willingness to buy unplanned items.	3.91	Agree
	Discounts and promotions are less likely to affect me when I'm in a negative mood.	3.98	Agree
	Average Weighted Mean	3.98	Agree
	Overall Average Weighted Mean	4.30	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree; 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree; 2.61 – 3.40 Neutral; 3.41 – 4.20 Agree; 4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree

Table 2 presents the factors affecting impulsive purchasing behavior among employees in Dapitan City in terms of store ambiance, store layout, product price, and personality and self-concept. The findings revealed an overall average weighted mean of 4.30, verbally interpreted as “Strongly Agree,” indicating that the respondents strongly agreed that these factors significantly influenced their impulsive purchasing behavior.

In terms of store ambiance, the respondents strongly agreed that the cleanliness and hygiene of the store made them feel comfortable and encouraged them to shop, which obtained the highest mean of 4.57. This was followed by well-organized product displays (4.44), attractive shelf designs (4.42), and a calm, air-conditioned environment (4.38), all verbally interpreted as “Strongly Agree.” The lowest-rated statement, although still interpreted as “Strongly Agree,” was the influence of lighting and décor on purchasing decisions, with a mean of 4.33. The factor obtained an average weighted mean of 4.43, indicating that store ambiance strongly affects impulsive purchasing behavior among employees. This finding is supported by recent studies which revealed that store atmosphere, cleanliness, lighting, music, and product displays create positive emotions that encourage consumers to engage in spontaneous purchases. Consumers are more likely to stay longer and buy unplanned items when shopping environments are comfortable and visually appealing (Parsad et al., 2023).

For store layout, the respondents strongly agreed that impulse purchases often happen when products are displayed near the checkout counter, which obtained the

highest mean of 4.26. Meanwhile, clearly marked categories and strategically arranged products both obtained means of 4.19, while sufficient aisle spacing received the lowest mean of 4.13, all verbally interpreted as “Agree.” The factor garnered an average weighted mean of 4.19, indicating that store layout moderately influences impulsive purchasing behavior. This suggests that product arrangement and strategic placement expose consumers to more items, increasing the tendency to make unplanned purchases. Recent literature supports this finding by emphasizing that store layout, shelf arrangement, and point-of-purchase displays positively influence consumers’ shopping behavior by increasing product visibility and shopping convenience (Chandrasekhar et al., 2024).

In terms of product price, the statement “I am more likely to buy products on sale, even if I don’t need them immediately” obtained the highest mean of 4.65, followed by purchasing decisions guided by price when on a budget (4.63), and the influence of discounts and promotions (4.62), all verbally interpreted as “Strongly Agree.” The lowest-rated statement was “I often choose cheaper options, even if it means compromising on quality” with a mean of 4.58, although still interpreted as “Strongly Agree.” The factor obtained the highest average weighted mean of 4.61, indicating that product price is the most influential factor affecting impulsive purchasing behavior among employees. These findings imply that discounts, affordability, and promotional offers create perceptions of savings and urgency, encouraging consumers to make spontaneous purchasing decisions. This result is supported by recent studies which found that promotional pricing and discounts strongly stimulate impulsive buying behavior because consumers tend to respond emotionally to perceived financial benefits and limited-time offers (Bhathena, 2025).

Lastly, in terms of personality and self-concept, the respondents strongly agreed that they tend to avoid unnecessary purchases when feeling tired or stressed, which obtained the highest mean of 4.27. On the other hand, shopping with friends leading to unplanned purchases obtained the lowest mean of 3.78, verbally interpreted as “Agree.” Statements related to emotional state influencing unplanned purchases (3.91) and reduced influence of discounts during negative moods (3.98) were also interpreted as “Agree.” The factor obtained an average weighted mean of 3.98, indicating that emotions, mood, and social interaction moderately influence impulsive purchasing behavior. This implies that consumers’ emotional conditions and social experiences contribute to spontaneous buying decisions. Recent studies support this finding by explaining that emotional responses, shopping enjoyment, excitement, and social influence significantly contribute to impulsive purchasing behavior because consumers often engage in unplanned buying to satisfy emotional needs and enhance positive feelings (Sohn & Ko, 2021; Parsad et al., 2023).

Table 3
Impulsive Purchasing Behaviors of Employees in Dapitan City

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Shopping without any intention to shop is always satisfying.	3.91	Agree
Whenever I purchase anything unplanned, I quickly think of the advantages and proceed to buy it.	3.85	Agree
I persuade myself to buy unplanned items if I like them (e.g., groceries, food, accessories, and clothing).	4.13	Agree
Every time I stop myself from buying anything outside my list, I end up purchasing more products.	3.89	Agree
I feel confident, independent, and unrestricted while shopping; the statement “I can shop whatever I want” is very attractive to me.	3.80	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.92	Agree

Legend: 1.00–1.80 = Strongly Disagree; 1.81–2.60 = Disagree; 2.61–3.40 = Neutral; 3.41–4.20 = Agree; 4.21–5.00 = Strongly Agree.

Table 3 presents the impulsive purchasing behaviors of employees in Dapitan City. The findings revealed an average weighted mean of 3.92, verbally interpreted as “Agree,” indicating that the respondents generally agreed that they exhibit impulsive purchasing behaviors during shopping activities.

Among the statements, “I persuade myself to buy unplanned items if I like them (e.g., groceries, food, accessories, and clothing)” obtained the highest mean of 4.13, verbally interpreted as “Agree.” This indicates that employees are likely to purchase products impulsively when they find them appealing or personally attractive. The result suggests that personal preference and product attraction strongly influence impulsive buying behavior among employees. Also, the statement “Shopping without any intention to shop is always satisfying” obtained a mean of 3.91, also interpreted as “Agree.” This implies that respondents experience satisfaction and enjoyment from unplanned shopping activities. Similarly, the statement “Every time I stop myself from buying anything outside my list, I end up purchasing more products” garnered a mean of 3.89, indicating that employees often find it difficult to resist unplanned purchases once they are exposed to shopping environments.

Meanwhile, the statement “Whenever I purchase anything unplanned, I quickly think of the advantages and proceed to buy it” obtained a mean of 3.85, verbally interpreted as “Agree.” This suggests that respondents tend to justify impulsive purchases by focusing on the perceived benefits or usefulness of the products before making a

buying decision. Lastly, the statement “I feel confident, independent, and unrestricted while shopping; the statement ‘I can shop whatever I want’ is very attractive to me” obtained the lowest mean of 3.80, although still verbally interpreted as “Agree.” This indicates that feelings of confidence, freedom, and independence moderately influence employees’ impulsive purchasing behavior. Thus, the findings indicate that employees in Dapitan City generally exhibit impulsive purchasing behaviors influenced by personal attraction to products, shopping satisfaction, emotions, and spontaneous decision-making during shopping activities.

In support, Dang et al. (2025), Ngo et al. (2024) and Mallari et al. (2023) all pointed out that employees exhibit impulsive purchasing behaviors influenced by product attraction, shopping satisfaction, emotions, and spontaneous decision-making. Employees tend to engage in unplanned purchases when they experience enjoyment, emotional gratification, and positive shopping experiences. Recent studies support that impulsive buying behavior is strongly associated with hedonic motivations, emotional excitement, product attractiveness, and enjoyable shopping environments, which encourage consumers to make spontaneous purchasing decisions and justify purchases based on perceived satisfaction and benefits.

Table 4
Relationship Between the Factors Affecting Impulsive Purchasing Behavior and the Purchasing Behavior of Employees in Dapitan City

Factors Affecting Impulsive Purchasing Behavior	Somer’s D Value	p-value	Decision Interpretation	
Store Ambiance	0.060	0.131	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Store Layout	0.212	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Product Price	-0.263	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Personality and Self-Concept	0.505	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Note. Significant at $p < .05$ level.

Accept Ho = Not Significant; Reject Ho = Significant.

Table 4 presents the relationship between the factors affecting impulsive purchasing behavior and the purchasing behavior of employees in Dapitan City using Somer’s D Test. The findings revealed that store layout, product price, and personality and self-concept had significant relationships with employees’ purchasing behavior since their p-values were lower than the 0.05 level of significance. In contrast, store ambiance showed no significant relationship with purchasing behavior because its p-value was greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

In terms of store ambiance, the computed Somer's D value was 0.060 with a p-value of 0.131, verbally interpreted as "Not Significant." Since the p-value was greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted. This indicates that store ambiance did not significantly influence the purchasing behavior of employees in Dapitan City. The finding suggests that although employees recognized the importance of cleanliness, lighting, and store comfort, these factors alone were insufficient to significantly affect their purchasing decisions. Recent studies support this finding by explaining that store ambiance may enhance shopping satisfaction but does not always directly lead to impulsive purchasing behavior, especially when consumers prioritize practical considerations such as price and necessity (Chandrasekhar et al., 2024).

For store layout, the computed Somer's D value was 0.212 with a p-value of 0.000, verbally interpreted as "Significant." Since the p-value was lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that store layout significantly influenced employees' purchasing behavior. The finding implies that strategic product arrangement, aisle organization, and checkout displays encourage consumers to discover and purchase unplanned items. Recent literature supports this result by emphasizing that effective store layouts increase product visibility and customer exposure to promotional displays, which stimulate impulsive buying behavior (Parsad et al., 2023).

In terms of product price, the computed Somer's D value was -0.263 with a p-value of 0.000, verbally interpreted as "Significant." Since the p-value was lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that product price significantly influenced employees' purchasing behavior. The negative relationship suggests that changes in price sensitivity may affect impulsive buying tendencies among employees. The finding implies that discounts, affordable pricing, and promotional offers strongly influence consumers' purchasing decisions. Recent studies support this finding by revealing that consumers are highly responsive to sales promotions, discounts, and price reductions because these create perceptions of savings and urgency that encourage impulsive purchases (Bhathena, 2025).

Lastly, personality and self-concept obtained the highest Somer's D value of 0.505 with a p-value of 0.000, verbally interpreted as "Significant." Since the p-value was lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that personality and self-concept significantly influenced employees' purchasing behavior. The findings suggest that emotions, self-perception, shopping enjoyment, and personal tendencies strongly contribute to impulsive buying behavior. Recent studies support this result by explaining that emotional states, hedonic motivations, self-expression, and psychological factors significantly affect consumers' impulsive purchasing decisions because individuals often engage in spontaneous buying to satisfy emotional needs and enhance personal satisfaction (Sohn & Ko, 2021; Parsad et al., 2023).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the employees in Dapitan City were mostly young to middle-aged adults, female, married, college graduates, belonging to the low-to middle-income bracket, and employed in the government sector. These characteristics suggest that the respondents were actively engaged in employment and purchasing activities, making them more exposed to impulsive buying tendencies.

The study further concluded that store ambiance, store layout, product price, and personality and self-concept influenced the impulsive purchasing behavior of employees. Among these factors, product price emerged as the most influential factor, indicating that discounts, promotions, affordability, and perceived savings strongly encourage impulsive purchasing decisions. Store ambiance also strongly influenced impulsive buying behavior, while store layout and personality and self-concept moderately influenced employees' purchasing decisions.

Moreover, the employees generally exhibited impulsive purchasing behaviors characterized by spontaneous buying, emotional attraction to products, shopping satisfaction, and unplanned decision-making during shopping activities. The findings suggest that employees tend to purchase products impulsively when they perceive enjoyment, emotional gratification, and attractive shopping experiences.

Lastly, the study concluded that store layout, product price, and personality and self-concept had significant relationships with employees' impulsive purchasing behavior, while store ambiance showed no significant relationship. This indicates that strategic product arrangement, affordable pricing, promotions, emotions, and self-perception significantly contribute to impulsive purchasing behavior among employees in Dapitan City.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it is recommended that business establishments and retailers in Dapitan City continue improving their store layout, product displays, pricing strategies, and promotional activities to attract consumers and enhance customer satisfaction while promoting responsible purchasing behavior. Retail managers and marketers may develop effective and ethical marketing strategies that encourage consumer engagement without excessively encouraging unnecessary impulsive purchases. Employees and consumers are also encouraged to practice proper budgeting, financial planning, and self-control in order to minimize unplanned spending and make more rational purchasing decisions. Moreover, consumers may increase their awareness of the emotional and psychological factors influencing impulsive purchasing behavior to help them manage their buying decisions more effectively. Lastly, future researchers may conduct similar studies in other areas and include additional variables such as social media influence, online shopping behavior, peer influence, and advertising exposure. Future studies may also utilize qualitative or

mixed-method research designs to gain deeper insights into consumers' experiences and decision-making processes related to impulsive purchasing behavior.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers strictly observed ethical standards throughout the conduct of the study. Permission to conduct the research was properly secured from the concerned authorities and respondents prior to data gathering. The respondents were informed about the purpose and objectives of the study, and their participation was entirely voluntary. Informed consent was obtained to ensure that respondents fully understood the nature of their involvement in the research.

Confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were maintained at all times. The information and responses gathered were treated with utmost privacy and were used solely for academic and research purposes. No names or personal identifiers were disclosed in any part of the study to protect the respondents' identity and welfare.

Furthermore, the researchers ensured that the study did not cause any form of harm, discomfort, or discrimination to the respondents. Honesty, integrity, and objectivity were likewise observed in the collection, analysis, interpretation, and presentation of data to maintain the credibility and reliability of the study. The researchers also ensured that all sources and related literature used in the study were properly acknowledged and cited to avoid plagiarism and uphold academic integrity.

In addition, the researchers utilized QuillBot as a supplementary tool for grammar checking, sentence improvement, and plagiarism checking to enhance the clarity, coherence, originality, and academic quality of the manuscript. However, all interpretations, analyses, conclusions, and final revisions remained the sole responsibility of the researchers to ensure the authenticity and integrity of the study.

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REFERENCES

- Azul, R. D., Cadano, K. D. Q., & Guiao, R. J. M. (2023). The impulse buying behavior and financial well-being profile of young professionals in the Philippines. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 13(3), 308.
- Basalma, E. (2024). Exploring the influence of gender, age, education level, and income on online impulsive purchasing behavior among college students. *Malaysian Journal of Business, Economics and Management*, 3(1).
- Bhathena, Z. (2025). A comparative study of impulse buying in retail stores and online platforms. *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research*, 13(3), 883.
- Chandrasekhar, K., Das, S., Gupta, N., & Jena, S. K. (2024). Comparative analysis of impulse buying behaviour across retail channels: A study of physical stores, e-commerce websites and mobile shopping apps. *Economic Affairs*, 69(2), 1109–1120.
- Chaudhuri, S., Kumar, A., & Bhardwaj, A. (2021). The impact of demographics on the impulse buying behaviour with respect to the purchase of grocery products. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, 12(8).
- Dang, T.-Q., Nguyen, L.-T., & Duc, D. T. V. (2025). Impulsive buying and compulsive buying in social commerce: An integrated analysis using the cognitive-affective-behavior model and theory of consumption values with PLS-SEM. *SAGE Open*, 15(2).
- Huo, C., Wang, X., Sadiq, M. W., & Pang, M. (2023). Exploring factors affecting consumer's impulse buying behavior in live-streaming shopping: An interactive research based upon SOR model. *SAGE Open*, 13(2).
- Mallari, E. F. I., Ato, C. K. A., Crucero, L. J. M. O., Escueta, J. T., Eslabra, V. A. P., & Urbano, P. E. M. (2023). The mediating role of impulse buying on hedonic shopping motivation and life satisfaction of online shoppers in the Philippines. *International Social Science Journal*, 1–12.
- Ngo, T. T. A., Nguyen, H. L. T., Nguyen, H. P., Mai, H. T. A., Mai, T. H. T., & Hoang, P. L. (2024). A comprehensive study on factors influencing online impulse buying behavior: Evidence from Shopee video platform. *Heliyon*, 10(15), e35743.

- Parsad, C., Prashar, S., & Vijay, T. S. (2023). Impact of store environment and consumer emotions on impulse buying behavior. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 70, 103152.
- Sohn, Y., & Ko, M. (2021). The impact of planned vs. unplanned purchases on subsequent purchase decision making in sequential buying situations. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 59, 102419.
- Urošević, A., Kocić, M., & Dukić, A. (2023). The influence of demographic factors on impulsive consumer behavior. *International Journal of Economic Practice and Policy*, 20(2).